

Toughening Epoxy Syntactic Foams with Milled Carbon Fibres

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Abstract

Syntactic foams comprising hollow glass microspheres (GMS) in an epoxy matrix are critical materials for lightweight structures, but their use is limited by their brittleness. Milled carbon fibres (MCF) were used to increase the energy absorption mechanisms in foams comprising ~60 vol% GMS. Weight ratios of up to 40% MCF:GMS were used. The tensile modulus of the foams increased with the addition of MCF. The tensile strength of the syntactic foam decreased with low loadings of MCF, but recovers when more MCF are added, and the mechanisms responsible are explained. The fracture energy of the syntactic foam increased by 183%, from 182 J/m² to 516 J/m², with 40% weight ratio of MCF. The toughening mechanisms were identified as crack deflection, debonding and subsequent plastic void growth, and fibre pullout. The simple and cheap addition of MCF greatly increases the toughness of the syntactic foams, enabling lighter or more damage-resistant structures.

Keywords

Syntactic foam, milled carbon fibre, microstructure, tension, fracture, toughening mechanisms, toughness, strength.

1 Introduction

Syntactic foams, comprising hollow glass microspheres (GMS) in an epoxy matrix, are critical lightweight structures which are extensively used in marine and aerospace applications, often as the core for sandwich composite panels. They are lightweight, buoyant and crush resistant, but their use is limited by their brittleness as they can fracture easily. Previous attempts to toughen syntactic foams in the literature have shown very modest improvements in toughness, ranging from 25-90% (1, 2).

In this study, foams comprising of ~60% volume fraction of hollow glass microspheres in an epoxy matrix were modified by the addition of milled carbon fibres (MCF), to introduce fibrous toughening mechanisms. The tensile and fracture properties of the syntactic foams were measured, and the toughening mechanisms were identified using scanning electron microscopy. Predictions using various models of the tensile modulus, tensile strength, and fracture energy are compared to the experimental data.

2 Experimental

The matrix for the syntactic foams is a standard diglycidyl ether of bisphenol-A (DGEBA) epoxy resin, cured with an accelerated anhydride. Borosilicate glass microspheres with a mean diameter of 40 µm were used to manufacture the syntactic foams. Milled carbon fibres with a mean diameter of 7.5 µm and a mean length of 100 µm were used as a modifier. The MCF were added in weight ratios with respect to the GMS, up to 40% MCF:GMS. The GMS and MCF mixture was embedded in the epoxy matrix to create the syntactic foam, using a confidential

manufacturing process. The GMS and MCF particles are randomly close packed, such that the volume fraction of all particles is kept at the maximum for all syntactic foam formulations to minimise density.

Uniaxial tensile tests were performed on the syntactic foams to determine the tensile modulus and strength according to the ISO 527-1 standard. The fracture toughness and fracture energy were determined using single edge notch bending (SENB) tests according to the ISO 13586 standard.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was used to observe the fracture surfaces of the SENB samples to identify the toughening mechanisms. Cross-sections of the syntactic foams were cut and cold-mounted using an acrylic resin. They were ground and polished to a 0.25 μm finish, and observed using an optical microscope to determine the microstructure.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Microstructure

Analysis of the optical micrographs (Fig. 1) of the syntactic foams showed that the fibres favour a 2D random planar orientation. Image analysis also showed that the volume fraction of the GMS decreases as the MCF:GMS weight ratio increases, suggesting that the MCF affect the packing of the GMS.

Fig. 1. Optical microscopy image of a cross section of MCF modified syntactic foam.

3.2 Tension

The tensile modulus of the unmodified syntactic foam was measured to be 3.36 ± 0.08 GPa. This increased to 5.42 ± 0.45 GPa with the addition of MCF at 40% MCF:GMS weight ratio, as expected due to the high modulus of the carbon fibre. The increase in tensile modulus can be predicted using the Halpin-Tsai model (3) for 2D planar randomly orientated fibres.

The tensile strength of the unmodified syntactic foam was measured to be 21 ± 2 MPa. A decrease in tensile strength was observed in syntactic foams modified with up to 8% weight ratio of MCF, but the strength recovers when the weight ratio is further increased. A model by Hull & Clyne (4) was modified to predict the decrease in tensile strength, showing excellent agreement to the experimental results, see Fig. 2. At high volume fractions of MCF the tensile strength agrees well with predictions using the model by Baxter (5). It is postulated that the transition in tensile strength is due to a structural percolation effect.

Fig. 2. Tensile strength of MCF modified syntactic foams, experimental data and analytical models.

3.3 Fracture

The fracture energy increased from $102 \pm 11 \text{ J/m}^2$ for the unmodified syntactic foam, to $517 \pm 34 \text{ J/m}^2$ for the 40% weight ratio MCF modified foam. The impressive 182% increase in fracture energy shows good promise for MCF as a toughener for syntactic foams. Fractography studies from SEM identified several toughening mechanisms: crack deflection caused by the GMS, fibre pull-out caused by the MCF, and debonding and subsequent matrix void growth caused by both GMS and MCF. Models to predict the fracture energy contributions (6) for each of the identified toughening mechanisms were applied, and summed to predict the overall fracture energy (7). The analytical and experimental results show excellent agreement, see Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Fracture energy of MCF modified syntactic foams, experimental data and analytical model.

4 Conclusions

Closely packed syntactic foams were modified with milled carbon fibres to increase the fracture toughness. The tensile and fracture properties of the modified syntactic foams were measured. The measured tensile modulus values showed excellent agreement to the Halpin-Tsai model. The tensile strength decreased at low loadings of MCF, but recovers at higher loadings. A Hull

& Clyne model, which was modified in this study, showed excellent agreement with the measured tensile strength at low loadings of MCF. A significant increase (of almost 200%) in fracture energy was achieved, which can increase the overall usefulness of syntactic foams in structural applications in the aerospace and marine industries. The toughening mechanisms were identified using SEM, and predictions from analytical modelling of these mechanisms showed excellent agreement with the experimental data.

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